

Reframing Sense of Belongingness: A Phenomenological Exploration of Lived Experiences in Diverse Team Roles

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Abstract

This study titled, "Beyond Titles: A Phenomenological Exploration of Lived Experiences in Diverse Team Roles," used a mixed-methods approach to investigate challenges, opportunities, support systems, and factors contributing to a sense of belonging within diverse teams. In lieu of this, majority of respondents were aged 25-34, followed by those aged 45-54, with 1-7 years of work experience being most prevalent. Findings revealed that respondents strongly agreed (weighted mean of 4.75) that their organizations foster continuous learning to support diverse teams. They also strongly agreed (weighted mean of 4.33) that employee resource groups effectively advocate for individuals; their teams promote inclusivity; and diversity positively impacts innovation and problem-solving. Participants strongly agreed (weighted mean of 5.0) that their roles are essential to team goals and that diverse roles are beneficial. A clear understanding of roles, the value of each member's contribution, and valuing input from all roles in decision-making also received strong agreement (weighted mean of 4.33). Regarding support systems, attending organizational training sessions and workshops received the highest agreement (weighted mean of 4.75). Participants also agreed (weighted mean of 4.0) on the usefulness of project management tools, technology, and external professional development activities. Feeling that one's work is meaningful and contributes to the team's success was a significant factor in fostering a sense of belonging (weighted mean of 4.75). Actively seeking diverse perspectives and feeling well-informed about team goals also contributed strongly to belongingness (weighted mean of 4.33 and 4.67, respectively). Furthermore, respondents emphasized the importance of professional values, continuous improvement, teamwork, and making a positive impact.

Keywords: *Diverse Team Roles, Lived Experiences, Teamwork, Phenomenological, Mixed – Research, Inclusivity, Diversity*